

Analytical Application of the Schiff Bases. Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III) with Disodium Salt of the Schiff Base Derived from 3-Aldehydosalicylic Acid and Ethylenediamine

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Disodium salt of the Schiff base, ethylenediamine-3-aldehydosalicylic acid, has been used as a reagent for spectrophotometric estimation of the trivalent iron. Optical density has been measured at 480 m μ and at pH range 7.2-11.5. The reddish yellow colour is developed instantaneously and is stable for about 24 hr. Sensitivity (Sandell) of the reagent has been found to be 0.022 γ Fe/cm². The interference of various ions in the measurement of the colour and the probable composition of the coloured species in solution have been studied.

Analytical applications of the Schiff bases have not been studied in detail. Duke¹ estimated copper gravimetrically in brass and bronze with salicylaldimine (salicylaldehyde ammonia Schiff base). Mukherjee² reported the colorimetric estimation of iron(III) with ethylenediamine-bis-sulphosalicylaldehyde and salicylaldehyde-glycine-hydroxamic acid. Singh and Kumar³ have recently studied the reactions of the Schiff base, bis-salicylaldehyde-ethylenediamine, with various metallic ions, including the applicability of the reagent for gravimetric estimation for copper. The present communication deals with the use of disodium salt of the Schiff base of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and ethylenediamine as a spectrophotometric reagent for determination of very small amounts of iron(III). The main advantage of this reagent is its high solubility in water, whereas the others, mentioned above, are sparingly soluble in water and are often precipitated during estimation in dilute aqueous solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the optical measurements were made with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer, using glass cells of 1 cm thickness. pH values of the solutions were measured with a Cambridge pH-meter.

A standard solution of iron was prepared by dissolving crystals of ferric nitrate (E. Merck, G.R. quality) in distilled water containing a few drops of nitric acid. The iron content of the solution was determined gravimetrically as Fe₂O₃ (1 ml soln. containing 0.1217 mg. of iron). Weaker solutions were prepared by dilution.

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3. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1962, 185, 211, 259.

A 1% aqueous solution of the reagent, disodium salt of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid-orthylenediamine, was used. Solutions of various other ions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of the chemically pure salts in distilled water. pH adjustments were made by using $N/10$ solutions of KOH and H_2SO_4 .

Absorbance Curves

To an aliquot quantity of iron solution, taken in a 25-ml flask, the reagent solution (5 ml) was added and its pH adjusted to 7.8. The volume was finally made to 25 ml. A reagent solution was also prepared under the similar condition. The optical densities of the reddish yellow colour were then measured against water blank at different wave lengths. Fig. 1, representing the results obtained by using 4 p.p.m. of iron, shows that the absorbances of the reagent and the coloured solution decrease gradually as wave lengths increase; but from 475 $m\mu$ to higher wave lengths, the absorbance of the reagent is very small. All the colour measurements were therefore made at 480 $m\mu$.

FIG. 1

Effect of pH and Reagent Concentration.—pH values of the solutions, containing 4 p.p.m. of iron (III) and 5 ml of the reagent solution, were adjusted to different values, the volume of each solution being made to 25 ml. Optical densities were then measured at 480 $m\mu$. Fig. 2 shows that the optical density values are constant at pH ranges of 3.4-5.1 and 7.2-11.5, although the intensity of the colour is less in the former pH range than in the latter. When pH values of the coloured solutions were raised above 11.5, the colour was gradually discharged with simultaneous precipitation, probably due to decomposition of the coloured species. The higher pH range was chosen for all practical purposes for obvious reasons.

The effect of the reagent concentrations on the colour system formed with 4 p.p.m. of iron and different amounts of the reagent, varying from 0.5 to 5 ml. was studied, maintaining the pH at 7.5-8.0. The results indicate that 3 ml of the reagent is sufficient for the maximum development of the colour.

FIG. 2

carried out with 0.8 to 15 p.p.m. of the metal.

Sensitivity.—Spectrophotometric sensitivity (Sandell) was calculated from the Beer law curve and was found to be $0.022\gamma \text{ Fe/cm}^2$.

The iron-reagent colour developed instantaneously and was stable for about 24 hr. Temperature in the region 20-50° had no effect on the colour.

Effect of Diverse Ions.—Ions like chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, acetate, fluoride, phosphate, citrate, molybdate, tungstate, oxalate, sodium, potassium, and ammonium did not interfere with the estimation of Fe(III) with the reagent. Vanadates, when present in large excess, interfered with the estimation.

FIG. 3

Composition of the Complex.—The composition of the complex of iron (III) with the reagent in solution was studied spectrophotometrically by Job's method of continued variations⁴. The absorption of the complimentary mixtures of equimolar solutions ($1.25 \times 10^{-4}M$) of iron(III) and the reagent in a volume of 40 ml, after proper adjustment of pH and dilution to 50 ml, were measured at 480 m μ . Fig. 4 shows the graphical representations of the optical densities against mole fractions. It appears from Fig. 4 that the complex species responsible for the colour has a metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 1 at both the lower and the

higher pH ranges. The composition of the coloured species in solution was also studied by the slope-ratio method⁵ and mole-ratio method⁶. These also indicate the formation of a complex of 1:1 metal/ligand ratio.

FIG. 4

Reproducibility.—Accuracy of the method was studied by analysing solutions containing known amounts of Fe(III). To aliquot quantities of Fe(III) solutions (0.5 to 3.0 ml), taken in a 25-ml flask, a 1% solution of the reagent (1.5 ml to 6.0 ml) was added; volume in each was made and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.5 ± 0.5 . The absorbances were measured in 1-cm cell at 480 m μ . The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Fe ³⁺ soln. taken. (p.p.m.)	O.D.	Fe ³⁺ found from Fig. 3.	% Error.
1.20	0.053	1.21	+0.83
2.40	0.105	2.40	± 0.00
3.60	0.157	3.59	-0.33
4.80	0.211	4.82	+0.42
6.00	0.261	5.97	-0.50
7.20	0.315	7.20	± 0.00

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